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November 20, 2020

SOCAR
“Gas Export” Department

To: **Ilham R. Mammadzadeh**,
Director of the Institute of Philosophy and
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Regarding the Review of the Monograph

Dear Professor Ilham,

Based on your letter dated November 3, 2020, No. 51/11-145, the monograph titled *“Gasification of Azerbaijan and the Operation of the Gas Industry (1955–1970)”* by dr. Aydın Alizadeh, Chief Researcher at the Institute and Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, has been reviewed by our department.

The submitted monograph is of great importance in terms of examining the historical, sociological, economic, political, and technical aspects of the establishment and development of the gas industry in Azerbaijan during the period of 1955–1970. Acknowledging the author’s diligent efforts, we express our gratitude and wish them success in their future endeavors.

Sincerely,
Akbar Hajiyeu
Head